

Increased Voltage Compensation and an Improved DVR Control Strategy

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Abstract:

This work focuses on using a fuel cell-powered dynamic voltage restorer to enhance the voltage quality of delicate loads during voltage sags (FC-DVR). By either 1) reducing the injected voltage's amplitude or 2) improving the dc bus energy support, the current control options either reduce the phase jump or increase the use of dc link energy. The study suggests an improved sag compensation technique that reduces load voltage sag while cutting down on overall sag compensation time. When compared to the current compensatory approaches, the proposed methodology significantly lengthens the FC- DVR sag support period (by more than 50%), according to analytical research. Simulator analysis is done to evaluate the effectiveness of the technique, and MATLAB/SIMULINK is then utilised to empirically support it. Keywords: BESS, DVR, SRF, and VSC.

I. INTRODUCTION

The demand for voltage-sensitive equipment has been rising, including programmable logic controllers (PLC), adjustable speed drives (ASD), air-conditioning controllers, computer centres, automated production lines, and medical equipment [1]. The reduction in voltage RMS between 0.1 and 0.9 PU over a period of 0.5 cycles to a few seconds is referred to as voltage sag. A rise in nominal voltage between 1.1 and 1.8 PU during a period of 0.5 cycles to 1 minute is referred to as swell. Voltage sags or swells in the power supply could be caused by faults or by big induction motors beginning. As a result, further machinery can stop working. Utilizing specialised power equipment, such as a dynamic voltage restorer, is a way to improve the quality of the Custom power devices are mainly of three categories such as series-connected compensators known as dynamic voltage restorers (DVRs), shunt-connected compensators such as distribution static compensators, and a combination of series- and shunt-connected compensators known as unified power quality conditioner [2]-[6]. The DVR can regulate the load

Voltage from the problems such as sag, swell, and harmonics in the supply voltages. Hence, it can protect the critical consumer loads from tripping and consequent losses [2]. The custom power devices are developed and installed at

consumer point to meet the power quality standards such as IEEE-519 [7].

Voltage sags in an electrical grid are not always possible to avoid because of the finite clearing time of the faults that cause the voltage sags and the propagation of sags from the Transmission and distribution systems to the low-voltage loads. Voltage sags are the common reasons for interruption in production plants and for end-user equipment malfunctions in general. In particular, tripping of equipment in a production line can cause production interruption and significant costs due to loss of production. One solution to this problem is to make the equipment itself more tolerant to sags, either by intelligent control or by storing ride-through energy in the equipment. An alternative solution, instead of modifying each component in a plant to be tolerant against voltage sags, is to install a plant wide uninterruptible power supply system for longer power interruptions or a DVR on the incoming supply to mitigate voltage sags for shorter periods [8]–[23]. DVRs can eliminate most of the sags and minimize the risk of load tripping for very deep sags, but their main drawbacks are the standby losses, the equipment cost, and also the protection scheme required for downstream short circuits. There are other DVR-based solutions and issues that they address, such as balancing the voltages in a three-phase system [8] and discussing energy-optimized DVR control in [10]. Industrial DVR examples are provided in [11], and [12] through [18] investigate various control strategies for various voltage sags. [19] presents a comparison of various topologies and control strategies for a DVR. [17] discusses the design of a capacitor-supported DVR that guards against sag, swell, distortion, or unbalance in the supply voltages. [24] discusses a DVR's performance when using a high-frequency link transformer. In this study, a reduced-rating voltage source converter is used to demonstrate how a DVR can be controlled and perform (VSC).

II. FUEL CELL

A fuel cell is a device that converts the chemical energy from a fuel into electricity through a chemical reaction of positively charged hydrogen ions with oxygen or another oxidizing agent. [1] Fuel cells are different from batteries in that they require a continuous source of fuel and oxygen or air to sustain the chemical reaction, whereas in a battery the chemicals present in the battery react with each other to generate an electromotive force (emf). Fuel cells can produce electricity continuously for as long as these inputs are supplied.

The first fuel cells were invented in 1838. The first commercial use of fuel cells came more than a century later in NASA space programs to generate power for satellites and space capsules. Since then, fuel cells have been used in many other applications. Fuel cells are used for primary and backup power for commercial, industrial and residential buildings and in remote or inaccessible areas. They are also used to power fuel cell vehicles, including forklifts, automobiles, buses, boats, motor cycles and submarines.

Fuel cells come in a variety of shapes and sizes, but they all have three basic components: an anode, a cathode, and an electrolyte that enables the movement of positively charged hydrogen ions (or protons) between the two sides of the fuel cell. Catalysts in the anode and cathode cause oxidation processes in the fuel that result in positively charged hydrogen ions and electrons. After the reaction, the hydrogen ions are pulled through the electrolyte. Direct current electricity is created at the same time that electrons are pulled from the anode to the cathode through an external circuit. Hydrogen

ions, electrons, and oxygen interact at the cathode to create water. Fuel cells are categorised according to the type of electrolyte they utilise because the electrolyte is what distinguishes the various types of fuel cells.

III. WORKING OF DVR

The schematic of a DVR-Connected system is shown in Fig. 1. The voltage V_{inj} is inserted such that the load voltage V_{load} is constant in magnitude and is undistorted, although the supply voltage V_s is not constant in magnitude or is distorted.

Fig.1. Basic circuit of DVR.

Injection schemes of the DVR. V_L (pre-sag) is a voltage across the critical load prior to the voltage sag condition. During the voltage sag, the voltage is reduced to V_s with a phase lag angle of θ . Now, the DVR injects a voltage such that the load voltage magnitude is maintained at the pre-sag condition.

The DVR is operated in this scheme with a Lithium-Ion battery energy storage system (LI-BESS). Fig. 2 shows a schematic of a three-phase DVR connected to restore the voltage of a three-phase critical load. A three-phase supply is connected to a critical and sensitive load through a three-phase series injection transformer. The equivalent voltage of the supply of phase a V_{Ma} is connected to the point of common coupling (PCC) V_{sa} through short-circuit impedance Z_{sa} . The voltage injected by the DVR in phase a V_{Ca} is such that the load voltage V_{La} is of rated magnitude and undistorted. The three-phase DVR is connected to the line to inject a voltage in series using three single-phase transformers Tr . L_r and C_r represent the filter components used to filter the ripples in the injected voltage. A three-leg VSC with Insulated-Gate Bipolar Transistors (IGBTs) is used as a DVR, and a LI-BESS is connected to its DC bus.

Fig.2. Schematic of the DVR-connected system

Fuel cells come in a variety of shapes and sizes, but they all have three basic components: an anode, a cathode, and an electrolyte that enables the movement of positively charged hydrogen ions (or protons) between the two sides of the fuel cell. By injecting or absorbing the reactive power or the real power, voltage sag adjustment utilising a DVR can be carried out [17]. Reactive power is used to compensate when the injected voltage is in quadrature with the current at the fundamental frequency, and the DVR has a self-supported dc bus. However, if the injected voltage and current are in phase, DVR injects real power; as a result, a fuel cell is needed at the VSC's dc bus. The method of control used Fig. 3 shows a control block of the DVR in which the SRF theory is used for reference signal estimation. The voltages at the PCC V_s and at the load terminal $V_{L,a}$ are sensed for deriving the IGBTs' gate signals. The reference load voltage V^* is extracted using the derived unit vector [23]. Load voltages ($V_{L,a}, V_{L,b}, V_{L,c}$) are converted to the rotating reference frame using abc-dq conversion using Park's transformation with unit vectors ($\sin, \theta, \cos, \theta$) derived using phase-locked loops.

Fig.3. Control block of the DVR that uses the SRF method of control

IV. SIMULATION AND MODELING

A. Simulink of Fuel Cell based DVR:

The Fuel Cell based DVR connected system consisting of a three-phase supply, three-phase critical loads, and the series injection transformers shown in Fig. 5 is simulated as follows.

Fig:5 Simulink of DVR based Fuel Cell

V. PERFORMANCE OF FUEL CELL BASED DVR

The performance of the Fuel Cell based DVR is demonstrated for supply voltage disturbances i.e voltage sag. At 0.1s, a sag in supply voltage is created. In this paper simulation results for both with and without Fuel Cell based DVR has been presented

A. Case: 1 DVR with BESS system.

In this case performance of the DVR has been observed without BESS, a voltage disturbance i.e voltage sag has been created at 0.1 and removed at 0.15s. Here the DVR injected voltage magnitude is 200V.

Fig.6. Performance of the DVR with BESS

B. Case: 2 DVR with Fuel Cell system.

In this case performance of the DVR has been observed with Fuel Cell, a voltage disturbance i.e voltage sag has been created at 0.1s and removed at 0.15s

Fig.8.PerformanceoftheDVRwithFuelCell

VI. CONCLUSION

The capacitor-supported DVR has been given a proposed improved sag correction mechanism. By shielding sensitive loads from grid voltage sags caused by the phase leap, the suggested technique enhances the voltage quality of such loads. DVR with BESS and DVR with FUEL CELL have both been demonstrated in this project. Due to its ability to maintain a steady voltage, the DVR with Fuel Cell can be utilised as a battery replacement, according to the simulation results.

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